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O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING
JIZZAX FILIALI

**ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION
TADQIQOTLARNING
DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI
VA RIVOJLANISH
TENDENSIYALARI:
YECHIMLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR
RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-TEXNIK
ANJUMAN MATERIALLARI
TO'PLAMI**

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THE ROLE OF INTERTEXTUAL INCLUSIONS IN ENGLISH-LANGUAGE POLITICAL COMMUNICATION

Elizaveta Aleksandrovna Vishnyakova, PhD in Philology
Lev Tolstoy Tula State Pedagogical University
vishnyalis@yandex.ru

Abstract: Political discourse is characterized by a fairly high degree of intertextuality. In English-language political communication, considerable attention is paid to intertextual inclusions borrowed from the speeches of political predecessors and used repeatedly by new politicians in new contexts, where semantic transformations are accompanied by the expectation of achieving value-oriented unity with the target audience based on a common volume and level of knowledge, including well-known realities and formulations that have occupied a firm place in the cultural and linguistic consciousness of society.

Keywords: political discourse, intertextual inclusions, linguistic economy.

The problem of language economy has not ceased to attract the attention of linguists since its coverage in the works of famous scientists, and first of all in the work of A. Martinet, who considers the “principle of economy in language” as the “principle of least effort” [1, p. 188]. This phenomenon is conditioned by both linguistic factors proper and heuristic factors: “The constant contradiction between the needs of human communication and his desire to minimize his mental and physical efforts can be considered as the driving force of linguistic changes. Here, as in a number of other cases, human behavior is subject to the law of least effort, according to which a person expends his energy only to the extent necessary to achieve a certain goal” [2, pp. 188-189]. All changes arising in this regard are, in one way or another, conditioned by one of the main functions of language – communicative. The process of linguistic economy can be considered in terms of lingua-creativity, taking into account the use of the potential of all levels of language in order to create optimal semantically capacious linguistic units with minimal human effort. A pressing issue in the field of linguistic economy studies is the problem of using ready-made models and linguistic complexes to convey messages. In this regard, the use of intertextual inclusions for the purpose of optimizing messages, while preserving their substantive potential, may be of particular scientific interest [1]. At the same time, intertextuality, with its own specificity, presents a particular problem in terms of the use of its representatives to convey messages, for example, due to possible modal differences inherent in the meanings conveyed by authors. The processes of implementing intertextual inclusions, both in the form of quotations and allusions in literary, artistic, and media texts, are characterized by their own peculiarities. A comparison of English-language allusive titles of literary and artistic works and the headlines of media reports revealed that the former typically feature a fairly accurate, abbreviated reproduction of the source of the

allusion, designed to ensure recognition by the addressee, who undoubtedly possesses specific background knowledge. The latter, however, feature "utterances well-mastered by the language community and easily recognizable to a mass audience" [3, p. 210].

Attention to media discourse, particularly the sphere of political communication, reveals factors that contribute to the active use of intertextual elements in this area [4]. Political communication is characterized by a significant number of intertextual inclusions of various types and is one of the most illustrative examples of the implementation of these phenomena, which optimize the speech process.

The communicative-pragmatic aspect of the study of intertextual inclusions in the research tradition is directly related to its role in the development of verbal communication. In political communication, an important task for the addresser is not only to achieve the recipient's understanding of the meanings implied in the statement, but also to exert a manipulative influence, to shape a new worldview in the target audience, to persuade, and to motivate them to take action. The choice of source for borrowing intertextual information, addressing specific linguistic material in its immediate understanding and identifying its implicit components, is also considered relevant. The issue of "integrating" intertextual inclusion into a new environment, its natural actualization in the new contextual conditions, taking into account the author of the borrowing text's objectives for achieving specific communicative-pragmatic and stylistic goals, and ultimately, to create a unity of values and orientation between the politician and their audience, is also significant.

Thus, intertextual inclusions represent not only a source of significant information and a means of creating a distinctive stylistic effect in the discursive space of the English language, but can also be considered a technique used to effectively and optimally convey the content of messages with minimal expenditure of speech effort and linguistic material. The determining factor in this case is the shared conceptual systems of the addresser and addressee, which allows for an adequate interpretation of the conveyed message, including its emotional, expressive, and evaluative characteristics, and the achievement of the necessary level of comprehension. In some cases, the use of intertextuality, which does not require extensive explanation, serves as a technique for implicit, politically correct presentation of information and exerts a communicative, pragmatic, and stylistic influence on the target audience by evoking certain emotions and associations in its members through accessing memory resources, as well as a means of establishing and maintaining contact between communicants based on a shared cognitive context.

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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GRICE'S MAXIMS OF THE COOPERATIVE PRINCIPLE IN COMMUNICATION

**Candidate of Philological Sciences, Associate Professor of
the Department of the English Language, Tatiana V. Drozdova**
Tula State Lev Tolstoy Pedagogical University
zel-ta@mail.ru

Annotation: The article touches upon the role of the cooperative principle in the process of speech interaction. To succeed participants should take into this principle in the process of speech interaction. On the assumption four categories under one or another of which will fall certain more specific maxims and submaxims that may be distinguished.

Key words: communication; utterance; cognition; cooperative principle; maxims of conversation, implicature.

The functional-cognitive paradigm which occupies an important place in modern linguistics is characterized by such distinctive features as expansionism, anthropocentricity, functionalism and explanationality. One of the areas of linguistic pragmatics along with the study of the pragmatic potential of linguistic units is the study and analysis of the principles of speech interaction as well as the rules and strategies with the help of which this process is carried out. Like any expedient activity, communication activity is subject to the principle of rationality. It means that, a person, wanting to achieve a certain goal, chooses an action that will allow them to achieve this goal faster and with minimal effort and resources. This idea was reflected in the already classic work of Paul Grice "Logic and conversation". The scientist introduced the concept of cooperative principle in his pragmatic theory. This principle is implemented in several postulates that P. Grice calls maxims – the maxim of quantity (be no less or no more than required), the maxim of quality (tell the truth, do not say what you do not have sufficient grounds for), the maxim of relation (be relevant – do not deviate from the topic), the maxim of manner (speak clearly, briefly and consistently) [3].

Compliance with the cooperative principle communication is a kind of "quasi-agreement" which is prescribed for all participants in the process of speech interaction. It is important to note that the participants in this interaction are determined to comply with this principle which is the basis for the implementation of various goals in the communication process.

Analyzing the aforementioned maxims in his work P. Grice notes the fact of the emergence of various doubts about this or that postulate. For example, with regard to the maxim of quantity, he believed that while in general the transmission of superfluous information was not a violation of the principle of cooperation, in some cases such superfluous information could sometimes be misleading, giving rise to